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“A TALE OF TWO TAILS”

From the windowpane she watches,
Golden eyes, slitted chin and furry skin
Her velvet paws silent on her
Polished wooden din.

The sun or moon paints stripe on across her back,
Each one has story to be told
On her nightly hunt
To fed her belly's crumbs.

Living on this busy city streets
Pungent and mess crips
Each living has its own dwelling battles
To survive every day of the hour.

On its search for food,
Of midnight hunts and secret nooks
Where ancient legend hold.

She purrs a tune of patients,
of worlds that move so slow.

Humming an eerie cry
Like someone is lurking on the side
From other realms that hides
Waiting, wondering when to strikes.

She only sees a group of mice passing by
Holding some greasy, smelly thing on their side
To survive this hunting game that we call life.

Her eyes change
she becomes a predator again

Walking slowly but precise
Waiting for the right moment to strike
To kill and survive.

But compassion and grace become hers,
She let them pass with ease
She thinks these mice might have a child
Waiting longing
For once she once called "Mom"
To her little kittens long gone.

She moves quietly away from those
Little mice she sees.

Going back to her kingdom
Her dominion of agony
Each corner was mapped and known.

A domain of softness shadows
Where her every need is sown.

She dreams of cream and comfort,
Of laps that lift her high,
Of gentle hands that brushes her fur
Beneath a starlit night

This is her tale, of ease and glam
That was ones belong to her
A love that never fades
In her memory of distant grace
Of how the world was made for her
in softness and sunlight
becomes quite shades of gray.

Beneath the old floorboards' scurries,
Small paws on dusty grounds
A soft squeaked and rattles
When midnight chime of clock sounds

Lightning, fast they move
For prey might catch them in disarray
Hunting for scrums to live
In the shit hole where they lived.

It's time to hunt
His whiskers twitch like antennas

Every sound arrived
Alerted his small body
It measures, weights and size
Each creak is a warning sign
It could be of relief or hope tonight

For mice like him
Survival is a must,
Each breath they take is a chance to vanish
Each moment half-divine.

He knows the cracks and corridors
And each alley of this neighborhood,
The crumbs that fall below,
Left over foods forget to throw
Is a blessing in this hallow glow

We need to move fast and precise
For hunter lurking on every side.

The places were darkness
Hides him from the foe.

But one single mistakes
His life and body would have no trace.

His heart beats fast,
like thunder rumbling in his chest.

His days are quick and sharp,
For he dances with danger to live a life.

He moves quick, of walls and wires,
Hidden paths where only he can go
And tiny creature could be a friend or a foe.

Once he survives the night,
He dreams of fields of grains,
Where freedom stretches wide and slow,
Of spaces vast and open,
where no predator can find him.

This tiny, brave adventure of him
Full of courage and will.

This is his tale-of speed fight
That never bends,
Of how he carves his place
in a world of giants rules his end.

And though this furry creature and less
may cross path again,
in distance and in size
whether in chase or sudden still.

Both dreams to survive in this romanticizing life.
Each holds their own truth
Tightly, respectfully
Each follows their own will

The cat sees order in calm, while
The little mice see life in every flight to fight.

Two different sides of living,
Two stories woven.

Of a tale of two tails to survive
In this game of life.

